

5G Demonstration on an EMDC with ML-Enabled Scaling and QKD-Secured Connectivity

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Abstract—This paper presents the implementation of a fully functional 5G network on a compact, energy-efficient edge micro datacenter, showcasing features such as workload prediction and preemptive scaling. The network extends across multiple edge micro datacenters and incorporates quantum-secure connectivity. Our demonstration provides a blueprint for forward-looking 5G deployments aiming to meet challenging latency and throughput requirements while complying with stringent security requirements. Measurements are performed for network throughput and latency as well as for CPU load of the different components of the 5G deployment, including distributed unit, centralised unit control and user planes, 5G core and the RAN intelligent controller. Additionally, an intelligent workload prediction mechanism, based on an LSTM model, enables preemptive scaling of the centralised unit’s user plane. This proactive approach helps to mitigate bottlenecks as the number of users connecting to the network increases.

Index Terms—5G, edge computing, mobile networks, preemptive scaling, quantum-secure communications.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE significant rise in demand for wireless data from both stationary and mobile devices presents new challenges for future mobile communication networks, including the requirement for fast data transfer, minimal latency, reliable and ubiquitous connectivity, and improved energy efficiency. Addressing these requirements necessitates new approaches and technologies, including those being deployed with modern 5th generation mobile (5G) networks, such as massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) configurations, virtualized radio access networks (vRANs), network function virtualisation and network slicing, as well as edge computing [1].

vRAN in particular allows dynamic deployment and management of radio access networks (RANs), offering network

This work was partially supported by the EU H2020 ECSEL JU project BRAINE (no. 876967), the EU HE JU SNS project 6G-SANDBOX (no. 101097560), the EU HE KDT JU project CLEVER (no. 101097560), as well as the the Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy (EZK), as part of the Quantum Delta NL programme.

operators and infrastructure providers enhanced operational efficiency and great flexibility to cater to the diverse requirements of 5G deployments for consumers or enterprise customers. The improved flexibility further enables operators to more dynamically address the challenges of varying and overall rising numbers of users/devices and of unequal quality of service for users at different locations within a cell [2], [3].

The introduction of new applications with stringent throughput and latency requirements – from industrial automation to autonomous vehicles and more – warrant a paradigm shift in network architecture towards the introduction of edge computing [4], [5]. The concept of edge micro datacenters (EMDCs) has gained substantial traction as a compelling solution offering compute and storage resources on-site or very near the user which tightly integrate with network infrastructure components. Driven by latency and network speed requirements, EMDCs have moved from a niche concept towards being a critical component for deployments aimed at supporting real-time applications and improved user experience.

While the combination of vRANs with EMDCs provides great flexibility and reduced latency, the ever increasing number of edge devices and their evolving functionalities pose challenges to resource management and elasticity. Precise forecasting of workload and utilisation of individual edge servers and entire EMDCs becomes crucial for maximising EMDC efficiency, minimising power usage and maintaining quality of experience. In vRANs, scaling of the central unit user plane (CU-UP) within an EMDC and across neighbouring EMDCs allows such optimisation – provided preemptive scaling can be performed based on accurate workload prediction, which in turn required real-time knowledge of central processing unit (CPU) and random-access memory (RAM) usage as well as network load and traffic patterns.

Dynamic workload scaling across neighbouring EMDCs further requires direct and high-speed fibre interconnections between EMDCs and to the mobile core. The latter then

are part of the critical network infrastructure supporting applications running on distributed compute resources and correspondingly require protection to ensure network security and data privacy. Forward-looking 5G deployments on and with EMDCs must thus incorporate future-proof security, i.e., be secure against future attacks enabled by quantum computers which will have the potential to break classic asymmetric cryptography [6]. Such security must be achieved without limiting the advantages offered by EMDCs – especially in terms of latency – and is thus best placed at infrastructural level [7]. Quantum key distribution (QKD) in combination with highly efficient layer 2 network encryption has been proposed to establish quantum secure interconnection between critical network elements, such as EMDC, with minimal added latency [8]. In this scheme, information theoretically secure key exchange is achieved through QKD, providing secret key material used to establish layer 2 tunnels with highly efficient, high data-rate symmetric encryption based on quantum-secure AES256-GCM which keeps added latency to a minimum (a few microseconds), comparable to that of an added switch or similar network element [9].

In this paper, the deployment of 5G network functions on a highly compact and energy efficient EMDC is demonstrated with machine-learning-enabled workload prediction and preemptive CU-UP scaling across two EMDCs. The EMDCs are interconnected with a quantum-secure link based on QKD, offering best-in-class security without negatively impacting network performance or latency. The demonstrated deployment of 5G on EMDCs offers unprecedented ease and speed of deployment, superior flexibility and reduced energy consumption. Together with a quantum-secure interconnection, the presented architecture and demonstration provide a blueprint for forward-looking 5G deployments where challenging latency and throughput requirements combine with the need for adaptive and heterogeneous compute and stringent security.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows: Section II discusses the deployment of 5G on the EMDCs and introduces the demonstration scenario, section III details the system setup and data collection infrastructure, while section IV describes the workload prediction and preemptive scaling architecture. Subsequently, section V presents and discusses the experimental results, followed by a short summary and conclusions in section VI.

II. DEMONSTRATION SCENARIO AND 5G DEPLOYMENT ON EDGE MICRO DATACENTRES

The system model and demonstration scenario have been chosen such as to represent a fully functional, complete end-to-end (E2E) 5G deployment blueprint for a future network with artificial intelligence/machine learning (AI-ML)-ready edge computing and quantum secure infrastructure connectivity. The system model is shown in Fig. 1 and consists of: a) an EMDC prototype with heterogeneous compute capabilities supported by the BRAINE middleware [10] utilising both Kubernetes and Docker swarm containers, b) a disaggregated 5G vRAN with the CU-UP and central unit control plane (CU-CP)

Fig. 1. System model for the demonstration of 5G deployed on an EMDC with AI-ML enabled CU-UP scaling and quantum-secure EMDC to EMDC interconnection based on QKD.

Fig. 2. Demonstration scenario showing the four phases. In phase 1 and 2 UEs successively connect and start downloading data, causing CU-UP CPU usage on EMDC1 to surpass the scaling threshold. In phase 3 and 4 workload prediction and preemptive scaling provide a second CU-UP on EMDC2, preventing surpassing the CPU load threshold.

deployed over the E1 interface, c) a slice-mitigation oriented scaling mechanism, and, d) a quantum-secure infrastructure connection between the two EMDCs based on QKD and efficient layer 2 network encryption. Finally, three 5G stand-alone (SA) ready mobile phones are included as end-user devices (user equipments (UEs)) to verify connectivity and evaluate network performance, as well as to demonstrate AI-ML based load prediction for preemptive CU-UP scaling.

The demonstration, proving the feasibility of such a quantum-secure-5G-EMDC blueprint, provides a benchmark for future deployments of highly virtualized AI-ML platforms equipped with open radio access network (ORAN)-based 5G connectivity that is delivered as cloud-native network function (CNF) and as such provides high scalability and adaptability towards varying traffic demands. In order to split elementary phone behaviours into separable groups, the demonstration has been divided into four phases, illustrated in Fig. 2: phase 1 is used to collect profiling data (such as CPU usage of the 5G vRAN components) in the situation where UE connect one by one, but do not transfer data; in phase 2 all the UE start to download constant bitrate traffic at 10Mbit/s each from a server on the EMDC; for phase 3 the system is restarted with the workload prediction and workload placement agents activated, tracking and analysing CPU load as UE connections arrive and predicting CU-UP load to perform preemptive CU-UP scaling, resulting in the deployment of a second CU-UP in phase 4.

It should be noted that in phase 1 and 2, as UEs connect and commence data download, the CU-UP CPU load on EMDC1 increases continuously and eventually surpasses the defined scaling threshold. Conversely, in phase 3 and 4, the increase in CU-UP CPU load is correctly predicted and a second CU-

UP is preemptively deployed on EMDC2, avoiding surpassing the threshold. The overall 5G deployment architecture and workload prediction and scaling workflow are presented in Fig. 3 and discussed in detail in sections III and IV.

III. DEMONSTRATION SETUP AND DATA COLLECTION

A. Demonstration System Setup

The demonstration system, based on the model presented in Fig. 1, utilises two custom EMDCs to run all 5G workloads and employs a USRP B210 software defined radio as remote unit (RU). Three 5G SA ready phones are deployed in fixed positions and operated remotely. The network operates in the 5G n78 band at a centre frequency of 3.43 GHz using a bandwidth of 40 MHz. The 5G deployment uses two of the eight available nodes in EMDC1 to deploy distributed unit (DU), central unit (CU) and 5G core network, while a single node in EMDC2 hosts the RAN intelligent controller (RAN), eXtended applications (xApps) and serves as target for CU-UP scaling.

Both EMDC provide heterogeneous compute consisting of four x86-64 CPU nodes, two graphics processing unit (GPU) nodes powered by NVIDIA Jetson AGX Xavier system on modules (SoMs), an ARM node with four ARM Cortex A72 CPUs and a storage node. All nodes in the EMDC are connected via a PCIe switch and have 10 Gbit/s Ethernet connectivity between them and to the outside world. It should be noted that while the EMDC provide substantial and heterogeneous compute capabilities, only a fraction of the EMDC resources is actually used in this demonstration to support the 5G network. The remainder of the EMDC resources has been used for demanding applications such as real-time face blurring, real-time object detection and tracking, audio location and tracking, as well as the deployment of digital twins for purposes as diverse as factory automation and optimisation and improved medical care.

The EMDCs are further unique in their highly efficient innovative thermosyphon cooling system in which nodes are housed in a monoblock, facilitating heat absorption by an evaporating coolant. The latter circulates between the monoblock and an external overhead air-coil condenser where the heat is exhausted to the environment. This system allows a fan-less design of the EMDC chassis reducing vibrations near the compute nodes and achieves substantially more efficient system cooling than traditional (edge)servers [11].

The quantum-secure infrastructure connection between the two EMDCs is implemented as shown in Fig. 1, providing a secure 10 Gbit/s layer 2 tunnel. This tunnel provides quantum-secure encryption of all data transmitted between the two EMDCs using the well-established Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) with a key size of 256 bit and using Galois/Counter mode (GCM) to ensure authenticated encryption [12]. Symmetric encryption with AES256-GCM is considered quantum-safe as using quantum computers provides limited speed-up of attacks compared to classical computers [13], [14]. Achieving quantum-safe encryption with AES however directly depends on the use of quantum-safe key exchange mechanisms for establishing of the shared symmetric key, ruling out current

asymmetric schemes. QKD, on the other hand, provides information theoretically secure (ITS) keys suitable to establish quantum-safe encryption with AES and is thus an integral part of the secure connection setup between the two EMDCs.

The secure connection setup thus is based on a pair of QKD transmitter and receiver, establishing a quantum channel over optical fibre for the exchange of quantum states used for key exchange via the coherent one-way (COW) protocol [15]. The two QKD devices are co-located with the two EMDCs and continuously exchange keys, achieving a secret key rate (SKR) of ≈ 2.5 kbit/s. While this key generation rate may appear low, it is easily sufficient for the 10 Gbit/s secure tunnel as only 160 bit of key material are needed to establish the tunnel and the same set of keys can be used to securely encrypt significant data volumes – typically on the order of several hundreds of gigabytes – before new keys are required to ensure continued secure operation [16], [17]. In the system demonstration, key rotation is performed in fixed time intervals, rather than based on actual traffic volume, ensuring that the chosen key rotation interval of 5 min is sufficiently small to remain below the mentioned limit even at full 10 Gbit/s link utilisation and resulting in an actual secret key consumption rate of $0.5\bar{3}$ bit/s.

The keys generated by the QKD devices are fed into a key management system (KMS) for key buffering and are made available via the application programming interface (API) specified ESTI GS QKD 014 [18]. A pair of high-speed network encryptors (Thales CN6140), also co-located with the EMDCs, is used to provide the quantum-safe encrypted layer 2 tunnel and configured to use key material generated by the QKD devices, which they request from the KMS over the aforementioned interface once per key rotation interval.

B. Data Collection

Time series monitoring data is collected throughout the deployed system and using a mixture of key performance metrics (KPM) monitor xApp and Telegraf, are stored centrally in a common InfluxDB time series database, and visualised using Grafana.. Statistics for CPU load, RAM occupation and network throughput are collected using Telegraf at an interval of 5 s at both container and node level. Telegraf is further used to collect metrics via SNMP from the involved network elements, layer 2 network encryptors and the QKD devices also at an interval of 5 s. Custom agents are deployed for monitoring of EMDC power consumption, cooling system behaviour and node and chassis temperatures. Monitoring data of the 5G network, including radio resource availability and usage, wireless throughput and performance as well as the number of connected UEs. Statistics for throughput and latency are further collected using standard iperf and ping tooling on both server and UE side.

A separate data collection process is in place to provide real-time CPU load data of the CU-UP1 container – as it clearly scales with the number of connected users and their activity – to the workload prediction agent. In this process CPU load data is exported using the docker status tool at a period of

Fig. 3. 5G deployment architecture and workload prediction and scaling workflow.

3s and sent to the PostgreSQL database from where it is received by the workload prediction agent.

IV. PREEMPTIVE WORKLOAD PREDICTION AND SCALING ARCHITECTURE

The overall 5G deployment architecture and workload prediction and scaling workflow are presented in Fig. 3. Therein, first, KPMs are continuously collected and delivered to the dedicated xApp KPM which make custom metrics available outside the RIC via the Y1 interface (step 2). The workload prediction agent employs a long short-term memory (LSTM) model to predict when additional resources will be required (step 3) at which point the workload placement agent triggers a scaling request (step 4) resulting in the deployment of an additional CU-UP container (step 5) together with the required interfaces (NG-U, E1, F1-U). Finally, an ‘E1 Setup Request’ ensures the appropriate interface between the user and control planes of the CU is set up (step 6) after which the new CU-UP is ready to serve new user connections.

Accurate prediction of future workload poses a significant challenge, as the sequential nature of time series data requires a model capable of capturing dependencies across time steps – here LSTM models represent an enhancement compared to recurrent neural networks (RNNs) [19]. Addressing the vanishing gradient issue inherent in RNNs, LSTM models excel in handling datasets with prolonged dependencies, making them particularly well-suited for time series problems.

All RNNs comprise a chain of repeating modules of neural networks, which in simple RNN has a very basic structure, e.g., a single tanh layer, and given some input x_t produce output h_t . LSTM models also have a chain-like structure [19], but with four neural network layers interacting in a specific way, where the core idea is the cell state C_t to which information can be added/from which information can be removed using so called gates. These gates allow optional information and consist of a sigmoid neural network layer and point-wise multiplication. Three such gates in the LSTM control and protect the cell state.

The first gate, the forget gate, decides what information will be discarded from the cell state and is given in Eq. (1). The

TABLE I
HYPERPARAMETERS FOR THE WORKLOAD PREDICTION MODEL.

Hyperparameter	Value
K	10
Batch size n	64
Learning rate η	1×10^{-3}
Sequence multiplier m	4

forget gate takes into account x_t and h_{t-1} and scales each element of C_{t-1} with a value between 0 and 1, where 1 refers to keeping the full state whereas 0 means discarding it. The next layer, tasked with deciding what information is added to the cell state, consists of two parts: first, a sigmoid layer called the input gate picks the values to be modified as in Eq. (2); second, a tanh layer outputs a vector \tilde{C}_t as in Eq. (3) with new values as possible additions to the cell state. The cell state is then updated as shown in Eq. (4) by multiplying the old state with f_t , making it forget what is needed, and adding new values after scaling with i_t . Finally, the output h_t is produced by a sigmoid layer deciding which elements of the cell state to output (Eq. (5)) and a tanh layer performing final scaling (Eq. (6)). One such LSTM cell followed by a dense layer is utilized for workload prediction. The model is optimised with the Adam optimiser; the loss used is mean square error (MSE) and all other parameters are given in Table I.

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f) \quad (1)$$

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i) \quad (2)$$

$$\tilde{C}_t = \tanh(W_C \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_C) \quad (3)$$

$$C_t = f_t * C_{t-1} + i_t * \tilde{C}_t \quad (4)$$

$$o_t = \sigma(W_o \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o) \quad (5)$$

$$h_t = o_t * \tanh(C_t) \quad (6)$$

Limited pre-processing is required before the data is fed into the LSTM model, transforming the sequential dataset into a supervised learning dataset by applying a sliding window and performing feature extraction. For any timestamp t the current and past N data points become the input $X^t = \{x^{t-N}, \dots, x^t\}$ and the next $t + K$ data points become the label $y^t = \{x^{t+1}, \dots, x^{t+K}\}$. As the collected data is limited due to the simplicity and constraints of the demo, data augmentation is performed to increase the time series dataset. This is performed by adding white Gaussian noise to the data and shifting the relative positions of different UEs joining the network, thus creating more data cycles. This training data allows the LSTM model to learn long-time dependencies and allows sufficiently accurate prediction of CPU load. The data is divided into 70 % training and 30 % test data, where validation data is 20 % of training data.

Workload prediction is performed for $K = 10$ steps in the future to allow time for scaling, effectively predicting the workload of the next 30s as the period of time series data collection is 3s. The number of LSTM units and the input sequence length are chosen in dependence on K , using a sequence length $M = m \cdot K$ that is an integer multiple of

Fig. 4. Prediction of CPU load for $K = 10$ and comparison to actual CPU load.

Fig. 5. Downlink throughput measured on the Open5GS container during phase 1 and 2 as well as phase 3 and 4 of the demo scenario.

K and $u = m \cdot K + 6$ LSTM units. A plot of CPU load prediction compared to actual CPU load is shown in Fig. 4 for $K = 10$ alongside the relevant standard deviation.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To evaluate the presented demonstration system, its performance and the preemptive scaling, a number of core statistics and key performance indicators (KPIs) is presented here. The results presented pertain to the execution of the demo scenario in the four phases shown in Fig. 2.

First, to validate correct operation of the 5G network, correct attachment of the UEs to the network is verified during step 1. In step 2 as UEs sequentially commence 10 Mbit/s download, downlink throughput of the Open5GS container is monitored, clearly showing the expected staircase behaviour with a peak rate of 30 Mbit/s, as shown in Fig. 5.

For the same steps CPU load is monitored as the most prominent indicator of system load and CPU load for the DU, CU-CP and CU-UP, Open5GS, and RIC containers are shown in Fig. 6. It is clear that the DU poses the largest requirements in terms of CPU load with an idle CPU load of approximately 150% (where 100% corresponds to full occupation of one CPU core) and scales linearly by approximately one core per active UE, reaching a maximum utilisation of $\approx 450\%$. The CPU load of the RIC and CU-CP containers show averages of $\approx 5\%$ and $\approx 10\%$ respectively independent of UE activity, while that of the Open5GS container clearly scales with the number of active UEs showing $\approx 10\%$ CPU usage per UE and thus overall remaining below 35% CPU load. The CPU load of the CU-UP container – under special scrutiny in this

demonstration – similarly clearly scales with the number of active UEs, but at a larger load of $\approx 25\%$ per active UE. As a result, the total CPU load of the CU-UP container approaches 80%, showing the need of preemptively scaling the CU-UP.

The observed throughput during phase 3 and 4, i.e., when repeating the attachment and successive start of downlink traffic of three UEs with active workload prediction and scaling, shows practically identical behaviour to that of phase 1 and 2, as expected. Similarly, DU, CU-CP, Open5GS, and RIC container CPU load follows the same patterns as for phase 1 and 2, again as expected. Contrary to the previous phases though, in phase 3 and 4 the instantiation of a new CU-UP prevents the CPU load of CU-UP1 on EMDC1 from surpassing 50% with the load of UE3 taken by CU-UP2 on EMDC2, showing the effectiveness of workload prediction and preemptive scaling in avoiding possible resource bottlenecks. Fig. 7 shows the comparison of CU-UP load between phase 1 and 2 and phase 3 and 4.

As one of the key benefits of introducing EMDCs – next to the added flexibility and improved energy efficiency – is the reduction of latency, evaluation of latency with and without scaling was performed. The measured round-trip latency of ping messages between the UE and CU-UP shows a mean of 30 ms with an average packet delay variation (PDV)/jitter of ≈ 0.75 ms and a maximum jitter below 1.1 ms. After scaling the CU-UP to EMDC2, no change is observed in mean latency, indicating an added latency well below 50 μ s – from previous experiments with the same layer 2 network encryption setup suggests added latencies on the order of 5 to 10 μ s [9].

It should be noted that while for experimental convenience the two EMDCs – and therefore the two encryptors – were located side-by-side and actual transmission distance for the traffic going to the scaling CU-UP on EMDC2 is below 10 m, all interfaces between the two nodes included relevant electrical to fibre optic and optical to electrical conversion hardware and used pluggables rated to 80 km of fibre transmission distance. Specifically, the relevant interfaces are the encrypted 10 Gbit/s data channel, as well as the QKD service and quantum channels – on all of which artificial attenuation of 10 dB was introduced, equivalent to a fibre distance of ≈ 50 km. Thanks to the fact that full optical hardware was included in the setup, the added latency that would be encountered when actually separating the two EMDCs by typical fibre distances of 20, 40 or even 80 km is entirely determined by the physical propagation delay of light in fibre of ≈ 4.87 ns/m, corresponding to added one-way latencies of ≈ 50 km. This shows that quantum-secure scaling with efficient layer 2 network encryption can be achieved across substantial fibre distances with added latencies well below 0.5 ms and thus with minimal impact on the latency reduction benefit achieved by introducing EMDCs.

Finally, from analysis of the metrics from the QKD devices and encryptors, it is clear that the data rates between the two EMDCs required for this scaling demonstration of ≈ 10 Mbit/s is only a fraction of the provided secure tunnel capacity

Fig. 6. CPU load of the different containers involved in the 5G network measured during phase 1 and 2 of the demo scenario: (left) DU CPU load, (right) CPU load of Open5GS, RIC, CU-CP and CU-UP.

Fig. 7. Comparison of CU-UP CPU load with and without scaling, showing CPU load remaining below 50% thanks to CU-UP scaling to EMDC2.

of 10 Gbit/s. Nonetheless, with a constant interval of 5 min multiple key rotations for the encrypted tunnel are encountered during the demonstration period without any impact on throughput or delay and that all key requests between encryptors and QKD devices were successful.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Deployment of a 5G network on an EMDC was demonstrated with intelligent workload prediction based on an LSTM model allowing preemptive workload scaling to prevent CPU load bottlenecks resulting from increasing UE numbers. Scaling was demonstrated across two EMDCs with the critical infrastructure connectivity secured by layer 2 network encryption based on information-theoretically secure keys from QKD. Expansive metric collection across the network was performed, showing CPU load for the individual components of the 5G deployment as well as throughput and latency performance. Round-trip latencies of 30 ms were achieved without any impact observed from scaling across EMDCs, preserving the latency benefit obtained from the introduction of edge computing.

The demonstrated deployment of 5G on an EMDC ready to handle heterogeneous compute workloads and enabled for machine learning and artificial intelligence such as underpins the workload prediction and preemptive CU-UP scaling which was shown to prevent CPU bottlenecks as more UEs become active on the network. Combined with quantum secure connectivity based on QKD between the two EMDCs, this demonstration

provides a blueprint for advanced 5G deployments combining stringent security with minimal latency and high throughput.

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